

Neuro-Integral Modeling: Order of 21st Century Brain Health Management

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ABSTRACT

Adapted Neurosciences are revolutionizing understanding of brain and its ability to change and adapt. With a personalized, proactive approach, Adapted Neurosciences are transforming the way we approach brain health and human wellbeing. Scientific publications on neurointegral methodology are marking a milestone in neuroscientific research. Adapted Neurosciences improve prevention, detection, correction and rehabilitation in health. This innovative approach combines cutting-edge technologies with ancestral practices to optimize cognitive performance and emotional wellbeing. Through case studies and rigorous research; adapted neurosciences demonstrate how neuro-plasticity and neuro-genesis - empower to improve quality of life. Neurofeedback improves cognitive and emotional performance. Virtual Reality facilitates relaxation and treatment of conditions. Artificial Intelligence transforms diagnosis and treatment. This paper deals with the case of a teenage subject who reportedly suffered from anxiety and shame. The paper presents the diagnosis and treatment undertaken for regaining her mental health.

Key Words: Adapted Neurosciences, Neurointegral Methodology, Virtual Reality, Anxiety and Shame.

I. INTRODUCTION

This is the case study of a Subject, medium built, average weight, normal vitals, 117 / 80 Blood Pressure and is a School going child @ 12 years on date of diagnosis. She is a single child. Except for emotional issues like anxiety, Subject has no signs of problems in relationship, death of family member, friend, job loss, financial problems, problems of housing, school, legal problems, arrests, divorce, parenting problems, victim of physical abuse, forced to have sex, victim of sexual abuse, afraid of partner or from

any member of your family. Subject has no vices of tobacco, alcohol, drugs and the like. She does not take part in Sports and games. She has undergone psychological and psychiatric treatment.

Reason for Consultation

Subject is a 12-year-old female student patient. The patient attended the consultation with her parents. They highlighted that no matter how much she studied, the Subject tended to constantly paralyze herself in the evaluations, they indicated that she is a sensitive, fearful young woman, without friends and very little interaction. Most of the time she stays in her room reading books and music. Despite being a reserved young woman, she expressed discomfort with her physical features, felt guilty for worrying her parents and causing them inconvenience, and was carried away by helplessness when faced with the possibility of changing her attitudes. She shared that she had been a victim of bullying due to her body complex; Anxiety and shame were part of the symptoms that the adolescent repressed. Subject took refuge in reading because that way she felt safe from scorn and humiliation. It is to be noted that passive victims express, both verbally and non-verbally, elements with which they can be analyzed, since they generally adopt a posture of fear, with their body folded in on themselves and their heads down. Reason for consultation was low self-esteem, isolation and poor academic performance. Extreme concern is observed on the part of her family, who accompany her in every activity.

Patient Evolution

Session No. 1

Objective: Evaluate the patient's condition, interview and analyze case.

Description: In the first session, the Subject arrived visibly anxious, showing sadness on her

face. As a therapist, I began the session by allowing her to freely express her feelings and thoughts. The Subject shared that she was experiencing bullying from some classmates at school. While exploring her school experiences, it was revealed that this was negatively affecting her self-esteem and academic performance. The Subject expressed feelings of isolation, avoidance of socializing with her peers, and difficulty concentrating on her studies due to anxiety and stress. I asked her to describe in detail the bullying situations and how she felt emotionally when they occurred. This gave me a clear understanding of their situation and needs. Together, we set goals for future sessions.

Activities

- Initial interview with the Subject.
- Detailed exploration of her school experiences.
- Bullying situations and their emotional effects.
- Discussion about the Subject's strengths and hobbies.
- Establishment of therapeutic goals for future treatment.

Observations

- The anxiety and sadness evident on the Subject's face indicate a significant emotional impact due to bullying.
- A relationship of trust was established during the session, which made it easier for the Subject to share her feelings and thoughts.
- The initial interview provided crucial information to understand the Subject's situation and design an effective treatment plan.
- The definition of therapeutic objectives will guide the therapy process and evaluate progress over time.

Session No. 2

Objective: Brain function training and brain gymnastics training

Description

- In this session, I approached the Subject in an understanding and friendly way to explain in a simple way how the brain works, focusing on the areas related to emotions and thinking. I used simple analogies and visual examples so the child could better understand these concepts.
- During the session, I explained how emotions such as fear and sadness can affect how her brain functions and, in turn, influence her behavior and well-being. My goal was for the Subject to understand that her emotions are

natural and that she could learn to manage them effectively.

- Later, I introduced the idea of brain gymnastics, comparing it to the physical exercise necessary to maintain a healthy body. I showed the Subject a series of fun cognitive exercises that involved games, puzzles, and creative activities. I explained to her that these exercises would help strengthen her mind, improve her concentration, and increase her confidence in her cognitive abilities.
- During the brain gym sessions, I worked alongside the Subject on challenges that suited her personal interests, which not only motivated her, but also showed her that she was capable of overcoming obstacles and succeeding in cognitive tasks. Throughout the process, I constantly reminded the Subject that her brain was malleable and could change and improve over time, encouraging her to celebrate her small achievements and use these positive experiences to strengthen her self-esteem.

Activities

- Explanation of brain function.
- Explanation of brain gymnastics.
- Brain gymnastics exercises.

Observations

The Subject showed interest and motivation in learning about the brain and brain gymnastics. Understood the concepts explained during the session. She enjoyed the brain gymnastics exercises. She felt more motivated and confident after the brain gym sessions.

Session No. 3

Objective: VR training and diaphragmatic breathing

Description

- During this session, my focus was to train the Subject in the use of virtual reality (VR) and the diaphragmatic breathing technique as effective tools to manage anxiety and improve her emotional well-being.
- I began the session by creating a calm and comfortable environment for the Subject. Next, I explained what VR was and how she could use it to create safe and relaxing virtual environments. I selected a VR experience that recreated a beautiful natural environment and asked the Subject to put on the headset and immerse herself in this virtual world.

- While exploring the virtual environment, I taught the Subject the technique of diaphragmatic breathing and we practiced it together. As the session progressed, the Subject began to feel more relaxed and calm. I reminded her that she could use diaphragmatic breathing at any time in her daily life when she felt anxious or stressed.
- At the end of the session, we talked about how she could apply these techniques in her daily life to manage anxiety and improve her emotional well-being.

Activities

- VR explained.
- Selecting a VR experience.
- Immersion in the VR experience.
- Teaching the diaphragmatic breathing technique.
- Diaphragmatic breathing practice.
- Review of how to apply the techniques in everyday life.

Observations

- The Subject showed genuine interest and motivation in learning about VR and diaphragmatic breathing.
- Understood the concepts explained during the session.
- Enjoyed the VR experience.
- She experienced a feeling of relaxation and calm after practicing diaphragmatic breathing.

Session No. 4

Objective: Monitoring diaphragmatic breathing training reactions with neurotechnologies.

Description

- In this session, my focus was on reviewing the diaphragmatic breathing technique and how the Subject had been applying it in her daily life. The Subject shared that she had been using diaphragmatic breathing when she felt anxious or overwhelmed, and noticed a decrease in the intensity of her emotions, which helped her feel calmer and more centered.
- Later, team introduced the neurofeedback and biofeedback part. Team explained to the Subject how these technologies allowed her to monitor her physiological responses, such as heart rate and brain activity, in real time. During the session, the Subject participated in practical exercises in which she observed how her physiological responses changed when she applied the diaphragmatic breathing technique.

- I showed her how her heart rate became more regular and her brain activity became more balanced when she relaxed and applied the technique. The Subject was also able to observe how her body reactions changed in times of stress and how they stabilized when she used diaphragmatic breathing.

At the end of the session, we talked about how the Subject could continue to use these tools in her daily life to manage stress and improve her emotional well-being.

Activities

- Review of diaphragmatic breathing technique.
- Diaphragmatic breathing practice.
- Introduction to neurofeedback and biofeedback.
- Practical neurofeedback and biofeedback exercises.
- Reflection on physiological reactions.
- Discussion on how to apply the tools in everyday life.

Observations

- The Subject showed motivation to practice diaphragmatic breathing and use neurofeedback and biofeedback tools.
- She experienced a decrease in the intensity of her emotions when using diaphragmatic breathing.
- She was able to observe how her physiological responses changed when she applied the diaphragmatic breathing technique.

Session No. 5

Objective: Conscious mindfulness session and contemplative exercises

Description

- Team began the session by creating a calm and welcoming environment for the Subject, where I explained to her what mindfulness was and how she could use this practice to connect with herself and manage her emotions.
- During the session, Team demonstrated mindful breathing exercises that allowed the Subject to focus her attention on her own breathing, releasing worries and intrusive thoughts. The Subject actively participated in the exercises and demonstrated a genuine interest in learning to be aware of her thoughts and emotions.
- We explored how mindfulness might help her respond more balanced to stressful situations and cultivate self-compassion rather than self-

criticism. Additionally, Team asked the Subject to keep an emotion journal, where she could freely express her thoughts and feelings without judging herself.

- During the session, we explore topics related to self-image, self-esteem, and how to build a kinder relationship with her. We work on identifying negative self-critical thoughts and replace them with more positive and realistic statements.

Finally, Team taught the Subject self-compassion exercises, encouraging her to treat herself with the same kindness and support that she would offer a close friend in challenging times. We concluded the session with a brief gratitude meditation, where the Subject reflected on the things, she was grateful for in her life.

Activities

- Mindfulness explained.
- Conscious breathing exercises.
- Discussion on the benefits of mindfulness.
- Introduction to the emotions diary.
- Exploration of self-image and self-esteem.
- I work with negative self-critical thoughts.
- Teaching self-compassion exercises.
- Gratitude meditation.

Observations

- The Subject showed genuine interest and motivation in learning about mindfulness and contemplative exercises.
- She actively participated in the exercises and reflected on her experiences.
- She showed increased interest in herself and her emotions, indicating positive progress in her treatment process

Session No. 6

Objective: Virtual reality and conscious walking

Description: I started the session by selecting a virtual environment that represented a beautiful natural landscape and asked the Subject to put on the VR headset to explore it. During this virtual experience, I encouraged the Subject to pay attention to the details of the environment, such as the sounds of nature and the feeling of being present in that place, which allowed her to relax and disconnect from her daily worries.

Team explained to the Subject how virtual reality could be an effective tool to reduce stress and anxiety. Then, we went outside and walked slowly through a nearby park. During the mindful walk, I taught the Subject to pay full attention to her senses

and practice mindful breathing exercises. The Subject was able to stay present in the moment and release tension during this experience.

Team concluded the session by talking about how the Subject could apply mindfulness and relaxation into her daily routine.

Activities

- Virtual walk.
- Conscious walk.
- Conscious breathing exercises.
- Discussion on how to apply mindfulness and relaxation in everyday life.

Observations

- The Subject showed genuine interest and motivation in the activities of the session.
- She actively participated in the activities and reflected on her experiences.
- She experienced a greater state of relaxation and decreased stress after the session, indicating positive progress in her treatment.

Session No. 7

Objective: Emotional control through chi kung

Description

- In this session, Team began by creating a calm and comfortable space for the Subject and then explained to her what chi kung was all about. Team showed her some simple chi kung exercises, including deep abdominal breathing and gentle movements. During the practice, Team explained to her how chi kung could help her release repressed emotions and develop greater awareness of her feelings.
- After completing the exercises, I encouraged the Subject to share how she felt before and after the chi kung session. We also talked about how she could incorporate these techniques into her everyday life to manage her emotions effectively.

Activities

- Explanation of chi kung.
- Practice deep abdominal breathing exercises.
- Practice of gentle chi kung movements.
- Discussion on how chi kung can help release repressed emotions.
- Discussion on how to incorporate chi kung into everyday life.

Observations

- The Subject seemed interested and motivated in the activities of the session.
- She actively participated in the activities and reflected on her experiences.

- She experienced a greater state of relaxation and a lower level of stress after the session, indicating positive progress in her treatment.

Session No. 8

Objective: Active listening and laughter yoga exercises

Description: In this session, I began by practicing active listening, allowing Subject to express how she had been feeling since our last meeting. Then, I introduced the practice of laughter yoga, teaching Subject some contagious laughter exercises. Together, we performed these exercises, which helped Subject release tension and improve her mood. We also discussed the importance of finding moments of joy in everyday life.

Activities

- Active listening.
- Laughter yoga practice.
- Discussion on the importance of joy.

Observations

- Subject was open and willing to talk about her concerns and challenges.
- She enjoyed the laughter yoga practice and experienced a feeling of relaxation and happiness after the session.
- Subject was able to identify positive thoughts and happy moments in her life, reflecting positive progress in her treatment.

Session No. 9

Objective: Progressive visualization class and mindfulness reinforcement

Description

- In this session, I focused on introducing Subject to the concept of progressive visualization as a technique that can help her control her anxiety and improve her emotional well-being. I began by explaining in detail what this technique is, highlighting how you can create a safe and calm mental space through imagination. I mentioned that progressive visualization is an effective tool for reducing stress and tension, as well as improving feelings of security and self-control.
- Next, we guide Subject together through a progressive visualization. I invited her to close her eyes, relax and immerse herself in her imagination as I led her to an imaginary place where she felt completely safe and at peace. During this process, I asked her to pay attention to all the details of this imaginary place, including the sounds, colors, textures, and sensations. Progressive visualization allowed Subject to experience a deep sense of

relaxation and well-being, which proved to be a useful technique for her.

- After the visualization, we spend time discussing her experiences and sensations during the practice. Subject shared how she felt calmer and in control of her emotions during the visualization, which gave her a sense of relief. We talked about how she could incorporate this technique into her daily routine to deal with times of anxiety and stress.
- In addition to progressive visualization, we also reinforce her understanding and practice of mindfulness. We talked about how mindfulness can help her stay present in the moment and respond in more balanced way to stressful situations. I provided practical tips on how to apply mindfulness in her everyday life, such as paying attention to her breathing and thoughts without judging them.
- In summary, this session focused on empowering Subject with effective tools to manage her anxiety and improve her emotional well-being. Progressive visualization and reinforcement of mindfulness were key aspects of this session and contributed to her continued progress in therapy. Subject demonstrated receptivity and motivation to apply these techniques in her daily life, indicating positive progress in her treatment.

Activities

- Progressive display explained.
- Progressive display.
- Discussion on mindfulness.

Observations

- Subject was receptive to progressive visualization and was able to experience stress reduction and relaxation during the session.
- Subject understood the benefits of mindfulness and expressed her motivation to practice it in her daily life, indicating positive progress in her treatment.

Session No. 10

Objective: Tapping class diaphragmatic breathing training

Description

- In this tenth session, we focus on two important techniques to help Subject manage her anxiety and improve her emotional well-being. We begin with the introduction and practice of tapping, a technique that combines the stimulation of specific points on the body with positive affirmations. I explained in detail how tapping works and how it can help release

emotional tension and reduce anxiety. Together, we did a tapping session, in which Subject learned to identify her worries and use this technique to shift her focus toward more positive and constructive affirmations.

- Next, we focus on diaphragmatic breathing training. We practiced breathing exercises that helped the Subject connect with her deep breathing and learn to use it as an effective tool to calm herself in times of stress. Subject demonstrated increasing skills in the practice of diaphragmatic breathing and was willing to incorporate it into her daily life.

Activities

- Detailed explanation of tapping and its process.
- Tapping session, identifying concerns and applying positive affirmations.
- Practice diaphragmatic breathing exercises to connect with deep breathing.
- Discussion on the application of these techniques in everyday life.

Observations

- Subject was receptive and participatory during the tapping session, demonstrating an adequate understanding of the technique and its application.
- During the practice of diaphragmatic breathing, Subject showed improvement in her ability to perform the technique effectively.
- Subject expressed her interest and motivation to incorporate these techniques into her daily life as tools to manage anxiety and improve her emotional well-being.
- She continued progress in therapy indicates an ongoing commitment to her mental and emotional health.

Session No. 11

Objective: Cognitive training with app

Description

- In this eleventh session, we focus on cognitive training using an app designed to help Subject identify and challenge negative thoughts. Explain to Subject how this process would work and how the app would be a valuable tool on her path to emotional well-being.
- Team selected specific exercises within the app that would suit Subject's needs and challenges. Subject used the app to record her negative thoughts and then worked together to challenge those thoughts using the tools provided by the app. Subject demonstrated a solid understanding of how to apply these skills in

her daily life and felt more empowered to address negative thoughts.

- In addition to cognitive training, Team talked about how she could apply these skills in real-life situations. Also discussed was how to use these techniques during times of stress or anxiety, which would help Subject deal with challenges more effectively.

Activities:

- Detailed explanation of cognitive training with the application.
- Selection of specific exercises to identify and challenge negative thoughts.
- Using the app to record and address negative thoughts.
- Discussion on the application of skills in real-life situations.

Observations

- Subject was receptive to cognitive training with the app and demonstrated strong skills in identifying and challenging negative thoughts.
- Subject felt empowered to use the app's techniques in her daily life.
- Her willingness to apply these skills in real-life situations is a positive sign of her continued progress in therapy.

Session No. 12

Objective: Virtual reality session with neurofeedback and biofeedback to monitor social phobia

Description

- In this twelfth session, a unique virtual reality (VR) experience was conducted with the goal of addressing Subject's social phobia. I began by explaining to Subject how this special session would work, in which they would use VR along with neurofeedback and biofeedback to monitor and control her emotional responses in simulated social situations.
- They carefully selected a VR environment that represented a common social situation, such as a school reunion or a party with friends. Subject was able to explore this virtual environment and see virtual people with whom she would interact during the experience.
- During the VR session, Subject's physiological responses were monitored using biofeedback. This included measuring their heart rate and skin conductance to assess their anxiety levels in real time. Additionally, neurofeedback was used to help Subject recognize and regulate her emotional responses by observing her brain

activity. She learned to identify moments when her anxiety increased and to work on regulating it.

- They worked together to set goals for gradual exposure to social situations in VR. Subject practiced the exposure while receiving real-time feedback on her emotional and physiological responses. This technique allowed her to learn to face her social phobia in a controlled and safe way.
- As the session progressed, Subject began to feel more comfortable in simulated social situations. The feedback she received from VR, neurofeedback, and biofeedback helped her understand how her anxiety manifested and how she could manage it effectively.

Activities

- Careful selection of a VR environment that represented a common social situation.
- Exploration of the virtual environment by Subject.
- Monitoring Subject's physiological responses using biofeedback, including measuring heart rate and skin conductance in real time.
- Using neurofeedback to help Subject recognize and regulate her emotional responses by observing her brain activity.
- Establishing goals for gradual exposure to social situations in VR.
- Practice of controlled exposure in VR.
- Receiving real-time feedback on Subject's emotional and physiological responses during gradual exposure.

Observations

- Subject showed a receptive and committed attitude towards the VR experience with neurofeedback and biofeedback.
- She learned to identify and regulate her emotional responses effectively thanks to real-time feedback.

Subject demonstrated notable progress in her ability to cope with social situations, suggesting significant progress in her treatment

Session No.13

Objective: Progressive visualization training

Description

I began the session by creating a calm and comfortable environment for Subject. Next, I explained what progressive viewing would entail and how it could benefit her. During the session, I guided Subject through a series of relaxing mental images. I helped her relax her body and mind

through breathing and mindfulness exercises. I asked Subject questions to stimulate her imagination and help her connect emotionally with the imaginary environment. After viewing, we share impressions about the experience.

Activities

- Creating a calm environment.
- Progressive display explained.
- Guide through relaxing mental images.
- Breathing and mindfulness exercises.
- Stimulation of the imagination through questions.
- Share impressions and reflections about the experience.

Observations

Subject was receptive to the progressive visualization and was able to relax and reduce stress during the experience.

During the visualization, Subject was able to identify the physical and emotional sensations she was experiencing.

Subject has demonstrated notable progress in her ability to relax and reduce stress, which is encouraging for her continued emotional growth.

Session No. 14

Objective: Active listening and yoga training

Description

I began the session by reinforcing the importance of active listening and allowed Subject to share her emotions and thoughts from the last session. I used specific questions to better understand the situations that caused anxiety and depression, which allowed Subject to express her thoughts more clearly and thoughtfully. Together, we analyzed her thoughts for negative patterns, which increased Subject's awareness of her own thoughts and emotions. Then, we continued with relaxation and breathing exercises, which helped Subject improve her capacity for emotional self-regulation. We discussed how she could apply what she was learning in her everyday life.

Activities

- Reinforcement of active listening.
- Share and explore emotions and thoughts.
- Identification of negative patterns in Subject's thoughts.
- Relaxation and breathing exercises.
- Discussion on the application of skills in everyday life.

Observations

- Subject demonstrated greater participation and commitment in the session.
- Subject was able to identify and challenge her negative thoughts effectively.
- Subject has independently practiced relaxation and breathing exercises, indicating her commitment to her continued emotional well-being.

Session No. 15

Objective: Family session contemplative techniques

Description

In this session, Subject's parents were invited to participate in a family session. I began by explaining the purpose of contemplative techniques and how they could benefit both Subject and the family dynamic in general. Then, I guided Subject's parents in practicing these techniques.

Activities

- Explanation of the contemplative techniques: Parents were provided with a clear understanding of how these techniques could contribute to Subject's well-being and improve the family relationship.
- Mindful Breathing Practice: Parents participated in a mindful breathing session, which helped them focus on the present and reduce stress.
- Guided Meditation: A guided meditation focused on compassion and support for Subject was conducted. During this meditation, the parents shared their thoughts and feelings with Subject, which encouraged open communication and mutual understanding.
- Discussion about practice at home: It was discussed how parents could continue practicing these contemplative techniques in the family environment, which could strengthen the connection between them and Subject.

Observations

- Subject's parents demonstrated a receptive and committed attitude to contemplative techniques.
- Subject felt supported and understood by her parents during the meditation, which could contribute to improving family dynamics and her emotional well-being.

Session No.16

Objective: EMDR desensitization session

Description

- In this session, eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR) therapy was conducted with Subject. I began by explaining what this therapy consisted of and how it would work to help Subject process and overcome the traumatic memory she had previously identified.
- Team worked to identify an objective, measurable memory that would serve as the primary goal of the EMDR session. This memory was related to social situations that had been a significant source of anxiety and fear for Subject.
- Once the goal was established, the therapist introduced the desensitization process using bilateral stimulation. This included moving the eyes from side to side in a controlled manner. During this process, Subject began to share her thoughts, emotions, and physical sensations as they arose.
- Team worked collaboratively with Subject to restructure her thoughts and emotions in relation to the traumatic memory. They focused on reducing the emotional intensity associated with the memory and promoting a more adaptive response.

Activities

- Explanation of EMDR therapy: Provide Subject with a detailed explanation of how EMDR therapy would work and what her goal would be in this session.
- Target Memory Identification: Identify a specific traumatic memory related to your social phobia.
- Desensitization process: The EMDR process was implemented with bilateral stimulation, where Subject focused on the memory while sharing her thoughts and emotions.
- Cognitive restructuring: Help Subject restructure her thoughts and emotions related to the traumatic memory, promoting a healthier emotional response.

Observations

- Subject experienced a significant decrease in the emotional intensity associated with the traumatic memory.
- Subject shared that she felt more capable of dealing with social situations and that she had learned to better manage states of anxiety and fear.

- This session marked an important step in Subject's process of overcoming social phobia and on her path to better emotional health.

Session No. 17

Objective

- Training and sequence of exposure to social phobia and cognitive app review

Description: In this session, my main focus as a therapist was the continuation of Subject's treatment, with special emphasis on gradual exposure to social situations and the review of cognitive application as an effective therapeutic tool.

Activities

- **Review of progress:** The session began with a review of the progress that Subject had experienced throughout her previous sessions. Together, we discussed how the techniques and strategies she had learned had positively influenced her life. We discussed her ability to cope with previously anxiety-provoking social situations and improvement in her symptoms related to major depressive disorder and generalized anxiety.
- **Gradual exposure:** We then proceeded to identify new social situations that still represented a challenge for Subject, but which she was willing to face gradually. These situations became our specific objectives for the presentation in this session. During the exposures, Subject applied the coping techniques she had previously learned, and we kept track of her anxiety level before, during, and after each exposure. This allowed us to evaluate her progress and make adjustments as necessary to her treatment.
- **Cognitive Application Review:** Additionally, we continue to work on using the cognitive application as an integral part of her treatment. In this session, we reviewed how Subject had applied the cognitive techniques she learned to specific social situations and how these applications had contributed to her overall improvement.

Observations

- Subject shared that although she still experienced some anxiety in social situations, she felt more confident and able to handle it effectively.
- The reduction in symptoms of her major depressive disorder and generalized anxiety was highlighted as a positive indicator of her progress in treatment.

- Gradual exposure remained an essential part of her therapy, and Subject was committed to facing her social fears in a controlled and safe manner.

Session No.18

Objective: Training sequence Brain gymnastics and art therapy exercise

Description: In this session, my main focus was providing Subject with activities designed to stimulate her mind and encourage creative expression.

Activities

- **Brain gymnastics:** We start the session with brain gymnastics exercises. These exercises are designed to stimulate different areas of the brain and improve mental agility. Subject actively participated in this activity, doing crosswords, puzzles and memory games. During each exercise, I promoted concentration and problem solving, which helped strengthen Subject's cognitive skills.
- **Art therapy:** After brain gymnastics, we immerse ourselves in an art therapy session. This form of creative expression is effective for working on self-esteem and self-expression. Subject chose to work on a personal art project that would allow her to explore her emotions and thoughts. Through art, he was able to express her feelings in a way that is often difficult to put into words.
- During the art therapy session, Subject created a work that represented her personal growth and achievements. I encouraged her to reflect on what she had accomplished in her life and how she felt about herself at that moment. This activity not only improved Subject's self-esteem, but also provided her with a means to express her emotions in a healthy way.

Observations:

- Subject participated actively and enthusiastically in both activities.
- During the brain gymnastics exercises, Subject demonstrated good concentration and problem-solving skills.
- In the art therapy session, Subject created an expressive and meaningful work of art that reflected her personal growth and achievements.

Session No. 19

Objective: Active listening session and neurofeedback review

Description: In this session, I focused on providing emotional support to Subject, reviewing her accomplishments, and addressing her concerns.

Activities

- **Active listening:** I started the session by actively listening to Subject. I provided a safe space for her to express any challenges she had faced in her daily life and how she felt about her treatment process. I encouraged open communication and listened empathetically.
- **Review of neurofeedback results:** Next, we review the neurofeedback results together. We used the objective data to assess how her brain was responding to the training and whether she had experienced improvements in her cognitive agility and anxiety levels. The graphs and statistics provided a quantitative view of their progress, which helped strengthen their self-assessment and celebrate their achievements.
- **Active listening:** After reviewing the results, we continue with another active listening session. Subject shared her concerns about the challenges she still faced in social situations and how she felt in her interactions with her peers. I listened carefully and provided emotional support, encouraging her to talk openly and honestly about her concerns.

Observations

- Subject noticed improvements in her ability to concentrate and manage stress, which indicated progress in her treatment.
- She also highlighted that she felt more confident and less self-critical, which suggested an improvement in her self-esteem.
- Subject expressed her concerns about the challenges she still faced in social situations, which was an important step in addressing her ongoing needs.

Session No. 20

Objective: Cognitive stimulation and mental agility training

Description: In this session, we focus on improving mental agility and stimulating specific areas of Subject's mind.

Activities

- **Advanced cognitive exercises:** We begin the session with more advanced mental agility exercises. These included complicated logic puzzles, challenging math problems, and strategy games. These exercises require a high level of concentration, problem solving and

abstract thinking, which stimulates and strengthens specific areas of Subject's mind.

- **Progress Record:** As we progressed through the exercises, I encouraged Subject to keep a detailed record of her progress and how she approached each challenge. This allowed her to measure her improvement over time and develop a greater awareness of her abilities and problem-solving strategies.
- **Critical thinking and creativity:** In addition to advanced cognitive exercises, we incorporate critical thinking and creativity sessions. Subject became involved in research projects and presentations, which gave her the opportunity to apply her cognitive skills more deeply and creatively.
- **Open and reflective communication:** During the session, I maintained open and reflective communication with Subject. She shared her thoughts and emotions as we worked through the most challenging exercises. This gave her the opportunity to build an even more positive self-image as she overcame cognitive obstacles.
- **Celebration of achievements:** At the end of the session, we celebrated Subject's achievements. We highlighted how she had improved her cognitive agility and self-esteem through the advanced exercises. I also reminded her that each challenge overcome brought her closer to her goals and that she had great potential to continue growing and developing.

Observations

- Subject actively participated in all activities, which shows her commitment.
- Demonstrated a high level of concentration, problem solving and abstract thinking in advanced cognitive exercises.
- She was able to keep a detailed record of her progress and how she approached each challenge, demonstrating her ability to self-reflect.
- Subject enjoyed the critical thinking and creativity sessions, suggesting a holistic approach towards her cognitive development.
- She appeared motivated and confident at the end of the session, indicating a positive mindset towards her personal growth.

Session No. 21

Objective: Family session cognitive training talk

Description: In this session, we focus on reviewing Subject's progress and discussing the techniques used during her treatment. We also provide recommendations for the future.

Activities

- **Progress Review:** We begin the session by reviewing Subject's progress. Subject shared how she felt more confident and capable in social situations and how her school performance had improved. We observed a significant change in her behavior, as she was more open and less shy.
- **Discussion of techniques:** We had a detailed discussion about the techniques that were used throughout the treatment. Subject's family expressed their gratitude for the comprehensive therapeutic approach and neurointegral methodology used.
- **Recommendations:** We emphasize the importance of continuing to practice the techniques learned at home to maintain and continue strengthening Subject's skills. We explored how Subject could apply these skills in various areas of her life, including social relationships and academic performance.

Observations

- Subject demonstrated significant progress in her cognitive agility and self-esteem.
- Subject's family was grateful for the support received throughout her treatment.

II. CONCLUSION

- During this time, we have worked together to address her emotional and cognitive challenges, focusing on her social phobia and symptoms of anxiety and depression.
- From the beginning, Subject demonstrated a great willingness to actively participate in her own recovery process. We begin with talk therapy sessions, giving her a safe space to express her thoughts and emotions. This paved the way to better explore and understand their concerns and triggers.
- As we progressed, we incorporated various therapeutic techniques. We begin by focusing on cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) to address her negative thought patterns and cognitive distortions. Subject dedicated herself to identifying and challenging these thoughts, which gradually improved her self-esteem and ability to manage stress.
- Additionally, we introduced mindfulness practices and relaxation techniques, which helped Subject control anxiety and cultivate greater awareness of her emotions. Graded exposure therapy was essential in addressing her social phobia. Subject showed admirable courage in facing her social fears and, over

time, experienced a significant decrease in her anxiety in social situations.

- To further strengthen her cognitive skills, we incorporate brain gym exercises and cognitive stimulation. Subject demonstrated remarkable mental agility when tackling advanced puzzles and logic exercises. She also actively participated in art therapy sessions, which allowed her to explore and express her emotions through art.
- The therapy was not limited to Subject alone; also included family sessions. Working with her parents strengthened communication and support within the family, which was critical to her recovery.
- Throughout treatment, Subject shared her triumphs and challenges, allowing us to adapt our therapeutic strategies according to her needs. We have celebrated her achievements, from her improved academic performance to her personal growth and increasing self-confidence.
- As her treatment concludes, Subject faces the future with a solid foundation of skills and a healthy mindset. She has demonstrated incredible resilience and is well prepared to face future challenges with confidence and a deeper understanding of herself.

Through a comprehensive therapeutic approach and 21 treatment sessions, she achieved notable improvements in several aspects of her life. Key takeaways include:

- **Improved Cognitive Agility:** Subject participated in cognitive stimulation and mental agility exercises, which resulted in significant improvement in her ability to concentrate, solve problems, and think abstractly.
- **Reducing social anxiety:** Gradual exposure to social situations and virtual reality therapy helped Subject reduce her social anxiety. She learned to handle social situations with more confidence and security.
- **Improved self-esteem:** Through art therapy techniques, active listening, and emotional support, Subject was able to explore and express her emotions, which contributed to greater self-esteem and self-acceptance.
- **Application of mindfulness techniques:** Subject learned mindfulness and relaxation techniques that she could apply in her daily life to reduce stress and anxiety.
- **Development of social skills:** Cognitive training and review of negative thoughts

helped Subject develop more effective social skills and change negative thinking patterns.

- **Family support:** Subject's family's participation in family therapy sessions and their support at home were essential for her progress.
- **Greater self-confidence:** Subject demonstrated greater self-confidence and a more positive attitude toward life and social interactions.
- **Academic Progress:** Subject also made improvements in her academic performance, reflecting her ability to focus and successfully face challenges.

In summary, Subject's treatment was comprehensive and focused on improving her emotional well-being, cognitive agility, and social skills. Throughout the process, Subject demonstrated notable improvement in these aspects and a higher quality of life in general.

Success Factors

- **Effective collaboration:** The therapeutic relationship between Subject and I was collaborative and trusting. This allowed for open communication and a good understanding of their needs.
- **Diverse Therapeutic Techniques:** A variety of therapeutic approaches, including cognitive behavioral therapy, mindfulness, exposure therapy, virtual reality, among others, were used to address the various dimensions of Subject's challenges.
- **Subject's active participation :** Subject demonstrated a commitment and willingness to learn and apply therapeutic techniques in her daily life.
- **Family support:** The involvement of Subject's family in the treatment and their support at home were key factors for her therapeutic success.
- **Individualized adaptation:** Treatment was tailored to Subject's specific needs and progress, ensuring a personalized and effective approach.
- **Use of technology:** Incorporating technology, such as virtual reality and cognitive therapy applications, provided additional tools and objective feedback.
- **Goal Setting:** Clear, measurable goals were established that allowed Subject to measure her progress and experience a sense of accomplishment.

- **Ongoing evaluation:** Regular evaluations were conducted to measure Subject's progress and adjust treatment as necessary.
- **Supportive environment:** A therapeutic environment of trust and support was created in which Subject felt safe to explore her thoughts and emotions.
- **Positive reinforcement:** Subject's progress was recognized and celebrated, which fostered her motivation and self-esteem.

III. RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Maintain Practice:** It is important that Subject continues practicing the techniques and skills she has learned during treatment. Consistency in practice will help strengthen and maintain her improvements.
- **Self-awareness:** Encourages continued self-awareness. Encourage Subject to continue reflecting on her thoughts and emotions, identifying negative patterns and applying coping strategies.
- **Application in Everyday Situations:** Help Subject apply the skills learned in everyday situations. For example, if she has practiced exposure to social situations, encourage her to use those skills in her social and academic life.
- **Social Support:** Continue to foster a socially supportive environment for Subject. Supportive family relationships and friendships are essential to her emotional well-being.
- **Stress Management:** Work with Subject on effective stress management strategies, as this will help her face future challenges with confidence.
- **Realistic Goals:** Set realistic and achievable goals with Subject. Setting short- and long-term goals can give her a sense of direction and purpose.
- **Follow-up:** Follow up periodically with Subject to evaluate her progress and make adjustments if necessary. Ongoing support from a mental health professional can be beneficial.
- **Self-care:** Encourage Subject to practice self-care regularly. This includes healthy habits such as a balanced diet, physical exercise, adequate sleep, and time to relax.
- **Resilience:** Teach Subject about emotional resilience and how to deal with challenges effectively. Life has ups and downs, and it is important that she feel prepared to face them.
- **Celebrating Achievements:** Continue to celebrate your achievements, big and small.

Positive reinforcement can maintain your motivation and self-esteem.

- **Open Communication:** Encourage open communication in your family. Be available to listen and talk about any concerns that may arise.

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